

Welcome to the 7th volume of the EU-HIP Newsletter!

Dear Reader, we wish you a warm welcome to the seventh edition of our Newsletter.

Recently, we held our Annual Meeting and Symposium in Helsinki. Besides giving you updates from the meeting; this is a great opportunity to introduce you to a related project from the hosting country – FinSurveillance. Additionally, EU-HIP has helped organize the 17th Medical Informatics Symposium in Croatia and you'll get a glimpse into that as well.

Let's dive into the news!

EU-HIP Symposium & General Assembly in Helsinki

First, we want to thank everyone who has participated in the EU-HIP Symposium either in-person or online. You have helped us push the project forward. If you didn't have the chance to participate or just want to refresh your memory, a short recap is ready for you.

Our project is now entering the final six months of its timeline. This photo finish it is the right time to present project achievements, consolidate outcomes and discuss sustainability pathways, which is exactly what the meeting held in Helsinki from 10th to 11th November was about. Progress in fulfillment of formal obligations was presented for each work package, followed by introductions to three projects which are in-line with activities on EU-HIP: JA STOCKPILE, JA CHESSMEN and FinSurveillance (which we will come back to later in this Newsletter). Representatives from DG HERA have updated the audience on the progress made in the development of ATHINA, which was followed by a use case workshop shortly after. Colleagues from SPMS, Portugal gave an oral presentation on AI Usage for Public Health Surveillance.

The two-day event finished with the General Assembly and fruitful discussions about the project's achievements. A rather short period in front of the consortium gives enough room to finish formal obligations and sub-initiatives on national level which are already in progress, but in order to achieve long-term sustainability beyond the project's duration participants agreed that engagement with other initiatives plays a key role, bundled with strategic planning on European, national and regional levels. Building a more resilient and interoperable Europe in the light of future health crises will take time and engagement from multiple stakeholders. We hope that EU-HIP will remain one of the core initiatives that aim to contribute to those goals.

FinSurveillance

Data controller:

- Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL)
- Social Insurance Institution (KELA)
- Finnish Food Authority
- Statistics Finland
- Others
- WP Work package number in FinSurveillance

The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) has started the project FinSurveillance - Integrating data sources to improve infectious disease surveillance in Finland in January 2025. The main goal of this project is to integrate data sources to create a comprehensive and sustainable infectious disease surveillance system. By doing so Finland will enhance data analysis, interpretation, reporting, and visualisation - delivering better data to systems such as the ECDC surveillance platform and wellbeing services counties, to decision makers and to the public. The project is recognised to be in-line with the activities performed in EU-HIP and as such represents an important brick in the wall of initiatives that make the landscape of high-quality data sources needed for rapid assessment and response to health threats.

[More about the Project](#)

17th Symposium of Medical Informatics in Croatia

The Croatian Society for Medical Informatics has organized its annual Symposium at the Teaching Institute for Public Health „dr. Andrija Štampar“ in Zagreb on the 27th and 28th of November 2025. This year's topic was „From data to decisions: connecting knowledge, expertise and technology in medical informatics“ reflecting the aim of the event - to open a space for conversation between professions that often operate in parallel, although they are deeply interconnected - healthcare professionals, IT professionals, data scientists, regulators, educators, but also students, as future change agents.

EU-HIP has recognized this event as an opportunity to present its work to a diverse group of experts in fields which are crucial for the successful implementation of our goals and deliverables. As a co-organizer we have prepared a block of workshops aimed at introducing the participants to our work. Pikka Jokelainen (SSI, Denmark) has kicked-off the workshop with the Introduction to EU-HIP. Miriam Saso (Sciensano, Belgium) has presented the Country visit report of Croatia. The block was closed with the presentation on Standardization of microbiological findings held by Emanuel Brađašević (CIPH, Croatia) and wrapped up with a discussion among participants.

[More about the Symposium](#)

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